

Digital Literacy Programmes for Older Men in Ireland

A qualitative study

AgeAction
Age Equality

DCU
Ollscoil Chathair
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Title Digital Literacy Programmes for Older Men in Ireland - A Qualitative Study

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About Age Action

Age Action is the leading advocacy organisation on ageing and older people in Ireland. Age Action advocates for a society that enables all older people to participate and to live full, independent lives, based on the realisation of their rights and equality, recognising the diversity of their experience and situation. Our mission is to achieve fundamental change in the lives of all older people by eliminating age discrimination, promoting positive ageing and securing their right to comprehensive and high-quality services.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents findings from a qualitative study examining the experiences of older men who have engaged in digital literacy (DL) programmes in Ireland, commissioned by Age Action Ireland. Older adults in Ireland, especially men over the age of 60, face notable challenges in engaging with digital technologies, and exhibit different needs and preferences relative to other age and gender cohorts. As Ireland moves toward fully digitised public services, the need to address digital exclusion, engagement and attitudes among this demographic has become increasingly important.

The research had two main objectives: (1) to narratively review national and international DL initiatives relevant to older adults (and specifically men), and (2) to evaluate the lived experiences of older Irish men who participated in Age Action's DL MEN programme through focus groups and a participatory design workshop.

The academic literature presented provides a contextual overview with respect to older men and their engagement in DL, and relevant international examples are offered to provide some comparative insight to DL programmes in Ireland. Overall, there is a distinct lack of gender-specific DL programme evaluations (quantitative or qualitative) which is a significant barrier to evidence-based

approaches to engaging older men in DL. Further research is especially needed to address this problematic gap.

The four key findings from the focus groups were:

1. (Responding to) the imperative to adapt;
2. Digital is emotional and social;
3. Practical skills to enable quality-of-life; and,
4. Targeted programme delivery.

A participatory design workshop with key stakeholders further highlighted the importance of person-centred, emotionally responsive, and gender-sensitive programme design. Taken together, the overall qualitative findings demonstrate that there are very positive experiences associated with the DL MEN programme. Alongside this positive feedback, it is clear that digital literacy efforts must evolve beyond unidimensional technical skills to consider the complexities related to emotional barriers, social isolation, and the diversity of life experiences among older men who may or may not wish to engage with DL programmes.

The report concludes with key recommendations for tailoring future digital literacy programmes to this group: focus on practical outcomes, prioritise social connection, embrace

flexible delivery methods, and respect participant autonomy with regards to differing engagement styles. With targeted interventions, older men can gain the confidence and skills needed to meaningfully participate in Ireland's increasingly digital society. It is clear that the DL MEN programme by AAI has strong potential to further scale-up to meet the needs and preferences of older men in Ireland.

SECTION 1: BACKGROUND

1.1 Context

Older adults are interested in having and learning digital skills and literacies; which can encompass everything from basic functions to digital means of staying connected, organization, pursuing leisure activities, managing media, enhancing their productivity, managing money, and managing their health (LoBuono, Leedah, & Maiocco, 2019). Older people in Ireland are significantly disadvantaged compared to their European counterparts with respect to digital literacy (DL). Data from 2021 demonstrate that a quarter of 55-74 year olds have never been on the internet, and of those that have, 43% have below basic skill levels. Of the over 75s, half have never been on the internet.

DL is intrinsically valuable as a means of supporting daily activities and community participation. Mounting evidence demonstrates that DL can be a positive intervention to: address social isolation and enable connectedness; enable access to resources within and beyond one's community; empower people through digital confidence and supporting autonomy; and support health needs. The pandemic has emphasised the importance of maintaining social

connection and likewise the value of digital tools in supporting this – however, the evidence is mixed for older adults successfully transitioning to digital social connections within the COVID-19 context. A 2021 rapid review found that pre-existing societal disparities in access to, and utilisation of, health-related digital technologies were exacerbated by COVID-19 (Litchfield, Shukla, & Greenfield, 2021).

1.1.1 Diversity of Older Adults: The Role of Gender

Older adults are a diverse demographic, varying in all aspects of lived experience from age—ranging from 60 by many definitions to centenarian and beyond—to personal factors such as gender, education, life history and socioeconomic inequalities. The potentially complex intersection of such differing needs and vulnerabilities must be accounted for in researching and understanding digital literacy, and when translating research to practice. For example, in Australia's national three-year digital inclusion programme (reaching over 580,000 older adults), data suggests that programme outcomes were far from uniform, reflecting diverse motivations, lifecourse experiences, needs and capabilities among older adults, countering existing research that can sometimes neglect these key differences (McCosker et al., 2021).

An important point at the outset is the rationale for considering gender segregation (or lack thereof) with respect to digital literacy and indeed the overall health and wellbeing of older adults. Notwithstanding a very large degree of similarity between genders, there is a consistent pattern within the academic literature which clearly shows notable gender differences in some key areas.

Across a range of health (lower life expectancy), wellbeing (lower help-seeking behaviours), and lifestyle (higher risk-taking, differing substance use) factors, men have exhibited varying trajectories which hold important implications for public health, intervention design and education.

The increased digitisation of life has presented new barriers and facilitators for older adults' engagement with new or existing technologies. A recent evidence review of 83 relevant studies concluded that older adults' attitudes towards emerging technologies are influenced by demographic factors (education, income), technology-specific factors (perceived ease of use, accessibility) and social contexts (Zhang, 2023). However, with respect to gender, this review also found that men were more likely to actively use a range of technologies (such as computers, smartphones, automated vehicles) and were seen as perceiving themselves as leveraging technology to prioritise autonomy and lifestyle management, sometimes in an effort to maintain a post-retirement

“worker/employed” identity. In contrast, women utilised technology for more relational purposes.

In the domain of digital health, a nationally representative study from Hungary (n=1723) recently examined the knowledge, habits and attitudes of the older population aged 65 and over (Gyórfy et al., 2023). Although the overall results of this study showed that nearly half of the respondents aged 65–74, and a third of the people aged 75 (or over), used the internet for health-related purposes (83.5% of people under 65), there were some gender differences. In terms of needs for digital solutions, it was men, those more highly educated, and those living in the capital who had significantly more needs for different types of digital technology. Moreover, for actual digital device use and digital health needs, men were found to have used significantly more devices.

As a result of the above patterns, there is a recognition from a range of stakeholders that designing programmes specifically for the differing needs of older men in particular will likely support more positive outcomes. Indeed, community-based initiatives such as Men's Sheds are especially insightful into the potential of gender-specific approaches, with emerging evidence that self-rated health, social isolation, and well-being all improve for men who participate (Foettinger et al., 2022).

In Ireland, there is emerging evidence of Men's Sheds effectiveness in

relation to subjective well-being, mental well-being, physical activity, social capital and healthy eating (McGrath et al., 2022). Of the available international evidence for the successes of Men's Sheds, the literature suggests that appropriate facilities, sufficient funding in addition to a participant-driven management and organisation. This chimes with other qualitative research on Men's Sheds whereby older men themselves state that there is a need for such male-focused community programmes to address isolation, learning needs, and support friendships (Nurmi et al., 2018).

There has also been insufficient attention to centering the primary stakeholders, e.g., isolated older adults, not only in the design of digital literacy interventions, but also in the assessment, implementation and reiteration of interventions. Indeed, the specific inclusion of older men in such research is a long-standing gap in the existing literature (Mannheim et al., 2019; Oh et al., 2021).

1.1.2 Research Objectives

To build upon previous reports and scientific literature in relation to older men and digital literacy, this project has two objectives. The first objective is to provide a rapid evidence review and narrative synthesis of relevant national and international programmes and practices for supporting digital literacy. Secondly, our next objective is to conduct a

qualitative investigation (using focus groups augmented with a participatory design) to gather older men's experiences of the DL MEN programme, with particular attention to programme roll-out, implementation, adoption, and scale-up.

1.2 Research Method

1.2.1 Evidence Review Approach

An academic narrative literature review approach was applied using agreed parameters between all stakeholders across selected databases to inform the following research objectives:

- Narrative synthesis of relevant areas of literature regarding the rollout of DL programmes for older men, incorporating relevant national and international perspectives.
- Qualitative evaluation of older men's experiences of the Age Action Ireland DL programme, with the view to informing future rollouts/scaling-up.

Between April and June 2025, the following academic databases were searched: PsycINFO, PubMed, WebOfScience and IEEE Xplore. We also searched for relevant grey literature using online databases (e.g., Google Scholar). We first implemented the search in PsycINFO, and then replicated it as closely as possible across the other databases. Search terms were identified in extant literature, database subject headings,

and pilot searches.

Using PEOS (Population, Exposure, Outcome, Study Type) to search databases, titles and/or abstracts containing keyword combinations aligned with PEOS categories were searched:

- 1) population: older adults;
- 2) exposure: digital literacy programme;
- 3) outcome: implementation.

Please see Appendix 1 for a detailed search strategy. Searching was supplemented with searches of Google Scholar.

1.2.2 Qualitative design - a two-part approach

Two focus groups (with 13 participants) and one participatory design session (with 6 participants) were hosted between April and May 2025 in Cork and Meath. The aim of the focus groups was to collect the experiences of men who had engaged with the DL programme and synthesise these findings to inform a subsequent participatory design session. The focus groups were designed to incorporate semi-structured questions regarding the overall experiences of older men who have participated in the DL programme, including both positive and negative aspects, and any notable reflections from the participants on the role of technology in their lives.

Participatory design is a broad design

methodology that prioritises the active involvement of the human (sometimes referred to as the service ‘user’) in the design process to ensure outcomes meet their specific needs (Schuler and Namioka, 1993). This approach was selected to ensure that the voices of older men and other stakeholders (such as DL programme facilitators and the wider AAI team) could be heard when both interpreting the outcomes from the focus groups, but also the evidence review, with the overall aim of thinking about the potential (re)iteration of the DL programme into the future. That is, taking all outcomes into account, how do key stakeholders envision the future of DL for older men in Ireland?

1.2.3 Recruitment Procedure

In keeping with prior reports for Age Action Ireland, recruitment was led out by AAI via established DL networks and convenience sampling. Owing to the tight timelines of the project, it was not feasible to recruit a representative sample from the population of men participating in the DL programme.

1.2.4 Analytic Method

We used Braun and Clarke’s (2022) method of reflexive thematic analysis to interpret the overall focus group and participatory design data. All data was transcribed and analysed using a deductive and inductive approach to interpret the overall themes.

1.2.5 Ethics

To ensure that all potential ethical issues were thoroughly appraised at the outset, a full ethics application was completed within Dublin City University (DCU). Full ethical approval was granted by the DCU Research Ethics Committee in advance of the qualitative research (DCUREC/2022/033).

SECTION 2: DIGITAL LITERACY NARRATIVE EVIDENCE REVIEW

This section begins by providing a brief perspective on digital literacy, and then briefly addresses Irish national policy. We then review programmes in comparable countries around the world, followed by a brief overview of programmes in Ireland. Finally, we review the scientific research literature.

2.1 Digital Literacy Background

There are several related concepts in the academic literature focused on the ability to negotiate the digital environment; ‘digital literacy’, ‘digital skills’, ‘digital competency’, ‘ICT literacy’, and others. These concepts have considerable similarities and are often used interchangeably, but can also be delineated by definition. We focus here on digital literacy. Digital literacy refers to the ability to use digital technologies, including computers, mobile devices, and the internet, to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information. It encompasses both technical skills and critical thinking, facilitating individuals’ effective navigation of, and participation in, digital environments. Whereas digital skills might encompass operation of devices and use of software, i.e., the technical skills, digital literacy also includes a set of cognitive and social–

emotional skills for accessing, evaluating, and handling information.

The European Union considers digital literacy to comprise five areas of competence; information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety, and problem-solving. Using the European Union’s definition, just over half of people, 56%, in the EU aged 16 to 74 had at least basic overall digital skills. As of 2023, the proportion of people who had at least basic digital skills was highest in the Netherlands (83%), Finland (82%), and Denmark (70%).

People with at least basic overall digital skills in 2023

(% of people aged 16-74)

2.2 Digital Literacy Policy Developments in Ireland

Increasing digital skills in the population is one of the biggest challenges within the European Union. The Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles states that everyone should be able to acquire all the basic and advanced digital skills they need. Yet, 46% of Europeans, in particular among older people, do not currently possess the necessary basic digital skills, which hinders the use of digital technologies for everyday tasks and access to online services.

As of 2022, Ireland is ranked 5th (behind the four Nordic countries) in the European Union on the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), which monitors countries' progress with respect to digitalisation.¹

Ireland set a target of 100% online provision of key public services, but it also aims to ensure that 90% of these services are actually used online by 2030. In addition, Ireland is taking measures to ensure that, by 2030, at least 80% of eligible citizens are using the digital identification solution MyGovID.

In September 2021, SOLAS, the state agency that oversees further education and training, launched a 10-year *Adult Literacy, Numeracy and Digital Literacy Strategy*² which included commitments to (i) reduce the share of adults in Ireland without basic digital skills from 47% to 20%, (ii) roll out a major national literacy awareness campaign, and (iii) set up a one-stop shop for all relevant information on literacy.

1. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-economy-and-society-index-desi-2022>

2. <https://www.solas.ie/alnd-strategy/>

Recent policy initiatives have included The Department of Communications, Climate Action & Environment Digital Skills for Citizens grant scheme, which focused on funding the provision opportunities to develop basic skills, concluded mid-2022. Programmes delivered under this scheme have included, for example, digital skills training in GAA clubs.

2.3 Digital Literacy Programmes Around the World

In this section, based on our review of extant grey literature, we provide an overview of digital literacy programmes in similar countries around the world, where such information is available. We specifically include an overview of programmes in countries at the forefront of digital literacy, Netherlands and Finland, as well as countries such as Estonia, which are digitally progressive. Globally, we found very few comparable, large-scale programmes to enhance digital literacy amongst older adults specifically, and no programmes targeted at older men specifically. We include here approximately eleven programmes from Estonia, Finland, Netherlands, New Zealand, and North Macedonia. Each of these is a small country (or relatively so in the case of the Netherlands), an OECD member (except North Macedonia), with a human development index ranking of 'very high'.

Programmes varied according to a range of characteristics:

- Target Group: Most programmes focus on older adults; some extend to general adult populations.
- Delivery Formats: Varied – in-person (group/individual), online (live or self-paced), and hybrid.
- Programme Themes: Ranges from basic digital skills to health tech, government services, and app-specific training.
- Support and Funding: Backed by national libraries, universities, NGOs, or international bodies like the UN.

Programmes are summarised below by country, with details available in Table 1 below.

In Estonia, several digital literacy initiatives target older adults, addressing both foundational and advanced digital skills.

- Digimentor, run from September 2023 to May 2024 by two secondary school students, was delivered in person to groups of older adults. The curriculum ranged from basic digital competencies to topics like artificial intelligence, reflecting a broad and forward-looking approach.
- Digismart Seniors also offers in-person sessions to older adults, although the structure (group or one-to-one) is not specified.
- The Resistiré: Age Is Not an Obstacle programmes (II and III), delivered in Estonia, Latvia, and

Lithuania, are structured around video lectures. While the exact delivery format of Part II is unclear, Part III is conducted via Zoom. Both editions target older adults, with additional attention in Part II to socioeconomic factors. These programmes include instruction on digital applications (e.g., Microsoft and Google tools) and situate digital skills within a broader framework of physical, cognitive, and social well-being.

In Finland, the OdigO Project, led by two Finnish universities, addresses older adults' digital competencies with a focus on community awareness and curriculum development. Rather than direct instruction, OdigO seeks to build systemic support and educational infrastructure for digital literacy among the aging population.

The Netherlands appears to have one of the more comprehensive ecosystems of digital inclusion initiatives catering to both older adults and the general population, often delivered through public libraries or non-profit associations.

- Digisterker and DigiVitaler are group-based, in-person programmes focused respectively on digital government services and digital health/care. Both are funded by the Dutch national library and delivered through local libraries.
- Klik & Tik targets individuals with little to no prior computer experience. Delivered online and self-paced, it offers a basic

introduction to digital tools, including internet use, email, and online payments.

- SeniorWeb is a private not-for-profit association targeting older adults, with instruction available in person, at home, or online. It operates through a network of 500 educational centres and relies heavily on volunteer instructors, often older adults themselves. Membership costs €40 annually, and volunteers often manage local centres.

New Zealand's Digital Literacy Training for Seniors is a state-funded, national initiative aimed at older adults, with particular outreach to Māori, Pacific, and Asian communities. The programme is delivered in-person, often in culturally appropriate settings, and seeks to:

- Promote essential digital skills,
- Address digital exclusion among at-risk groups,
- And support the sustainability of training efforts over time.

North Macedonia's E-Seniors on Board programme, delivered under the auspices of the United Nations Development Programme, focuses on digital inclusion for older persons. It is delivered in person, although the format (group vs. one-to-one) is unspecified.

These programmes reflect a growing international commitment to older adults' digital literacy, with delivery formats ranging from self-paced online modules to in-person

community sessions. Many leverage local institutions (like libraries), are run by volunteers, and appear to rely on public funding. Several go beyond digital skills to engage with broader themes of social inclusion, health, and empowerment. Information about programme content is limited, and

any information related to experiences, outcomes, or the evaluation of implementation is almost entirely unavailable and is anecdotal; at a scientific level, there is no data available on programme outcomes or evaluation.

Table 1. Digital Literacy Programmes around the World

Country	Prog title	Target Population	Delivery Format	Prog Type	Link
Estonia	Digimentor	Older adults	Group, in-person	Digimentor was a project conducted from September 2023 to May 2024 by two high school students in Estonia, supported by a multinational telecomms company. Delivery was group based and covered a range of topics from basic, practical skills to artificial intelligence.	https://becid.eu/useful-material/in-sights-from-estonias-digimentor-project-and-strategi-es-for-advancing-media-literacy-among-older-adults/
	Digismart Seniors	Older adults	In-person (whether group or one to one is unknown)	Digismart seniors is a free digital literacy programme for older adults offered through the central library in Estonia's capital, Tallinn.	https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/ee-ageing_in_digital_societies-country_report.pdf https://keskraamatukogu.ee/ru/senioid-digitargaks/

	<p>Resistiré: Age Is Not an Obstacle II</p> <p>(also offered in Latvia and Lithuania)</p>	<p>Older adults (considers both age and socio- economic status)</p>	<p>Video- lecture based. Mode of delivery is unclear</p>	<p>A 20-hour programme that covers the internet, word processing, presentations, smart devices, social networking, and internet security. Part of a wider programme also that addresses multiple aspects of older adults’ physical and cognitive health, well-being, and community participation.</p>	<p>https://resistire-project.eu/better-stories/bridging-the-age-gap-and-fostering-lifelong-learning/</p> <p>https://vanuseioletakistuseks.ee/et/projekti-kohta</p>
	<p>Resistiré: Age Is Not an Obstacle III</p> <p>(also offered in Latvia and Lithuania)</p>	<p>Older adults</p>	<p>Video lectures delivered via Zoom</p>	<p>An apparent update of Age Is Not an Obstacle II. Appears to focus more directly on Google and Microsoft apps, such as OneDrive, Drive, Outlook, Gmail Edge, Chrome, Excel, Google Maps, Google Slides, etc.</p>	<p>https://vanuseioletakistuseks.ee/et/vanuseioletakistuseks-iii/vanuseioletakistuseks-iii-materjalid</p>
<p>Finland</p>	<p>OdigO– project (The Skillful Tutors of Adults’ and Aging Population’s Digital Competence s to Lapland)</p>	<p>Older adults</p>	<p>Community awareness and curriculum development</p>	<p>OdigO–project is an online programme aimed at increasing awareness in the community of the need to support older adults’ digital literacy and related curriculum development initiatives. Operated by two universities in Finland.</p>	<p>https://digital-skills-jobs.europa.eu/en/inspiration/good-practices/odigo-project-lapland-finland</p>

Netherlands	Digisterker	Adults/ General	Group, in-person	Digisterker assists with digital government, and is made available by local libraries across the Netherlands (as funded by the Dutch national library, Koninklijke Bibliotheek).	https://www.digisterker.nl/werken-met-de-overheid/
	DigiVitaler	Adults/ General	Group, in-person	DigiVitaler is an online educational programme, offered in libraries in the Netherlands, which assists people with aspects of digital health or digital care. (Funded by the Dutch national library, Koninklijke Bibliotheek).	https://www.digisterker.nl/digivitaler/
	Klik & Tik	'Anyone who has hardly or never worked with the computer'	Online, self-paced	Klik & Tik is aimed at all adults, not specifically older adults. Basic introduction to computer literacy: how to start and switch off, use a mouse, type, use the internet, pay for things online, use email.	https://overoefenen.nl/programma/klik-en-tik-de-basis/
	SeniorWeb	Older adults	In-person or at home or online	SeniorWeb, a private not-for-profit association, offers volunteer-led courses at 500 educational centers across the Netherlands, as	https://www.seniorweb.nl/

				<p>well as online and at home. Volunteers not only give lessons, but also often are responsible for organising a local education centre. Volunteers tend to be older adults themselves. Members of SeniorWeb pay €40 per annum.</p>	
New Zealand	Digital Literacy Training for Seniors - this includes a variety of programmes	Older Adults. There are a range of progs tailored for specific demographics (e.g., older adults in the Māori, Pacific, or Asian communities)	In-person, including in culturally appropriate settings	<p>National, state-funded digital literacy programme. According to the dissemination materials, the Digital Literacy Training for Seniors programme aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support participants to learn essential digital skills • target older population groups at greater risk of digital exclusion • improve the sustainability of digital training programmes for older adults 	<p>https://www.superseniors.msd.govt.nz/ourwork/digital-inclusion/digital-literacy-training-for-seniors</p>
North Macedonia	E-Seniors on Board: Ensuring Digital Inclusion for Older Persons	Older adults	In-person (whether one-to-one or group delivery is unclear)	A programme delivered under the auspices of the United Nations Development Programme	<p>https://www.undp.org/north-macedonia/new-seniors-board-ensuring-digital-inclusion-older-persons</p>

2.4 Digital Literacy Programmes in Ireland

In addition to searching for international practice and programmes, we scoped digital literacy programmes in Ireland. Aside from Age Action's DL MEN programme, a range of digital literacy and digital skills programmes exist across Ireland. We focus our overview here on programmes available to and targeted at older adults, as well as some programmes targeted at other groups who may experience a digital divide or other forms of socioeconomic inequality, exclusion, or marginalisation and who may have digital literacy needs.

There tends to be very limited information available publicly with respect to the content of the programmes, and virtually no detailed, publicly accessible information about programme outcomes, evaluations, or implementation.

Based on our review, most programmes in Ireland are delivered on a small or local scale, with few if any being delivered in more than a single or very small number of locations. Programmes have been delivered through settings as diverse as libraries, local development groups, and GAA clubs. They have been funded, organised, or delivered by such organisations as local Education and Training Boards (ETBs), Further Education and Training (FET), county councils, local development networks, partnership companies, and

the voluntary sector/charities.

Initiatives have been aimed at a wide range of groups or populations, including: the general population, older adults, men in the Traveller community, migrant communities, people in long-term unemployment, people using family homeless services, people in direct provision, and people in the Roma community. Programmes often seem to focus on practical digital skills, which may or may not encompass broader digital literacy concepts and material. Programmes appear to generally be delivered in group format. Some innovative or atypical approaches worth noting include: Louth Local Development's SMART Café which uses a drop-in café approach (as has a pilot programme from Dublin and Dún Laoghaire ETB), Dublin's Northside Partnership's Life in Motion, which develops digital and other literacies via creation of mini documentaries on digital devices, and Coiste Forbartha Chnoc Fola's Siúlóid Nádúr Digiteach which combines nature walking with related digital skill development.

Government has funded a wide range of literacy programmes, including digital literacy and digital skills, annually via the Adult Literacy for Life³ mechanism.

In Table 2 below, we provide a selective overview of programmes available throughout Ireland.

3. <https://www.adultliteracyforlife.ie/fund/>

Table 2. Selected Digital Literacy Initiatives in Ireland

Programme	Target Population	Detail	Provider	Location	Link (as available)
<i>AI in Everyday Life: A Digital Citizenship Literacy Project</i>		Upcoming programme aimed at improving understanding of AI technologies and their everyday applications. Focuses on safe, responsible AI usage, and emphasises critical thinking and digital literacy to counter misinformation.	Limerick and Clare Education and Training Board College of Further Education and Training	Limerick and Clare	Not available
<i>Byte and Brew</i>	Older adults (but may include others)	Four three-hour digital skills classes delivered in four locations in each of the counties listed	Cavan and Monaghan Education and Training Board	Cavan and Monaghan	https://www.cavanlibrary.ie/events/upcoming-events/byte-andbrew.html ↓
<i>Computers for Beginners/Improvers</i>	Over 16s	Part-time, free course aimed at beginners. Self-paced, with the possibility to work toward a recognised certificate	Kildare FETC	Kildare	https://kildarefetc.ie/computers-for-beginners-improvers/
<i>Connect Cork: Smartphones Made Easy when life becomes Digital</i>	Older adults, people who are long-term un-employed, people with language needs	Tailored digital smartphone literacy programme	Northside Community Enterprises	Cork	https://www.nce.ie/community-enterprise-cork/news/free-digital-skills-training

<i>Digilit</i>	Adults		Wicklow County Council Library Service, in partnership with Kildare and Wicklow Education and Training Board (KWETB)	Wicklow	https://lgiu.org/blog/article/bridging-the-digital-divide-wicklow-county-councils-one-to-one-digital-project/
<i>Digital Literacy Community Peer Led Innovation (2025)</i>	Active retirement group members, members of the Traveller community	Training for active retirement group members and members of the Traveller community as digital literacy peer mentors, delivering digital literacy to long term unemployed clients and members of projects supporting people in addiction recovery.	North East West Kerry Development Programme	Kerry	Not available
<i>Digital Skills Clinics</i>	Adults		Cavan and Monaghan ETB and County Libraries	Cavan, Monaghan	https://www.northernsond.ie/news/free-digital-skills-clinics-launched-in-local-libraries-225459
<i>Digital Skills for GAA Members</i>	Adults	10 hours of training, delivered free to the recipients, and shaped for groups' requirements. Content includes internet, email, websites, online services, banking, apps.	Meath Partnership (a private entity) in collaboration with Moynalvey GAA, Kilkenny GAA Dublin and Dun Laoghaire Education and Training Board		Example: https://moynalveygfc.ie/digital-skills-training/ Example: https://kilkennygaa.ie/2017/05/digital-skills-for-citizens/

<i>Digital Skills Training Project</i>	Parents in direct provision	Workshops on school apps, online resources for parents of school-aged children, and staying safe online.	Serve the City Ireland	Dublin	Not available
<i>DLR Libraries Financial & Digital Literacy 'Smart Cafe'</i>	General	Piloting of a smart café over 8 weeks in Ballyogan Library. Informal sessions on financial and digital literacy.	Dublin and Dún Laoghaire Education & Training Board (DDLETB) Adult Education Service	Dublin	Not available
<i>Empowering Digital Literacy Champions</i>	Diverse communities, including Syrian, Ukrainian, Roma, Traveller, and older adults within the community	Aim: Train 20 digital literacy champions for diverse communities	Westmeath and Longford County Libraries	Westmeath and Longford	https://www.independent.ie/regional/longford/news/six-longford-and-westmeath-projects-aimed-at-tackling-adult-literacy-demands-land-60k-c
<i>Life in Motion</i>	Older adults, people in recovery	Digital literacy, literacy, and numeracy skills development via the creation of documentaries on mobile phones and tablets.	Northside Partnership CLG	Dublin	Not available
<i>Neighbour Net: Digital Skills for a Family Homeless Service</i>	People in Respond Family Homeless Service	Four-week tailored digital skills programme, each consisting of four workshops.	Dublin and Dun Laoghaire Education and Training Board (DDLETB) - Southeast	Dublin	Not available

<p><i>Siúlóid Nádúr Digiteach Loch an Inbhir</i></p>	<p>Older adults</p>	<p>Nine-week digital skills course for older adults integrating the Irish language with digital education. The course focuses digital apps that may enhance the person's experience while walking the siúlóid nádúr, or nature walk.</p>	<p>Coiste Forbartha Chnoc Fola</p>	<p>Donegal</p>	<p>Not available</p>
<p><i>SMART Cafés</i></p>	<p>Older Adults (aged 55+)</p>	<p>Drop-in, café style learning environment, which runs over two weeks for each of beginner (introduction to smart phones, digitally connecting with others) and advanced (cybersecurity and digital payments, services, and hobbies) offerings.</p>	<p>Louth Local Development in collaboration with ALONE</p>	<p>Louth</p>	<p>https://www.dundalkdemocrat.ie/news/local-news/1662554/louth-local-development-host-event-for-older-people.html and, https://www.thebarbican.ie/events/smartlcafe-2024-10-01/</p>
<p><i>SMART EDGE: Smartphone Efficient Digital Government Engagement</i></p>	<p>Roma community migrants (International Protection Applicants)</p>	<p>8-week course. Topics include smartphone digital proficiency, accessing public services and banking</p>	<p>North East West Kerry Development Programme (NEWKD)</p>	<p>Kerry</p>	<p>Not available</p>

<p><i>Unlocking Digital Skills</i></p>	<p>Adults</p>	<p>Digital skills programme that aiming to support adults to set up MyGov ID accounts and assist them in navigating online government services</p>	<p>Westmeath and Longford County Libraries</p>	<p>Longford & Westmeath</p>	<p>https://www.independent.ie/regional/longford/news/six-longford-and-westmeath-projects-aimed-at-tackling-adult-literacy-demands-land-60k-cash-injection/a120840451.html</p>
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2.5 Implementing Digital Literacy Interventions

Digital literacy programmes may be delivered in public settings, in private homes, or in blended format. Such public spaces can include libraries, adult education facilities, third age university, community centres, leisure centres, and drop-in centers (Schirmer et al., 2023) or smart cafés⁴. Most contemporary digital literacy programmes seem to focus on smartphones and tablets, with slightly less emphasis on computers or laptops (Schirmer et al., 2023). The evidence around programme roll-out is mixed. Available international evidence is limited in various ways with respect to applicability to Ireland's case. One example from a comparably high income, but uniquely urbanised Singapore, shows that demographic factors, such as higher education, being part of the ethnic majority, and having lower initial digital literacy, are associated with greater willingness to enrol in digital literacy education programmes (Soundararajan et al., 2023). Evidence and recommendations from other countries such as Armenia (Arion et al., 2024) or China, for interventions promoting digital literacy in isolated groups, may or may not be directly applicable to Ireland's socio-economic landscape, stage of digitisation, or sociocultural and economic priorities.

Schirmer and colleagues (2023) have identified that barriers and facilitators to implementation fall into four categories. For facilitators, the categories are support (access to social support, continuous support, peer learning, and intergenerational learning), training (an interest-driven curriculum, adaptation of the programme to individual needs, access to technology, addressing fears, gaming, observational learning, and demonstrations). For barriers, these are either internal (learners' lack of confidence, fear, or physical limitations), or external (ageism, teaching methods, i.e., information overload, individual needs not addressed, lack of flexibility). We review some of these and other factors—differences between older adults, the learning environment, and attitudinal barriers—as deemed relevant below.

4. <https://www.dundalkdemocrat.ie/news/local-news/1662554/louth-local-development-host-event-for-older-people.html>

2.5.1 Differences Between Older Adults

To implement programmes, there is a need to understand who is likely to take them. Older adults, and older men too, are a diverse group. Mixed-methods research (latent class analysis of two time points and qualitative interviews) has been undertaken on a large-scale digital inclusion programme for over-50s in Australia that involved online learning modules presented through a government Web portal, and face-to-face support provided by a community-based organisations (McCosker et al., 2023). What they found by statistically clustering programme participants according to a range of sociodemographic, attitudinal/emotional, skill, and participation variables and following up the analyses with interviews was three distinct groups of participants: ‘emerging learners’, ‘accomplished learners’, and ‘evolving learners’. ‘Emerging learners’ tended to have limited prior opportunity for engagement with digital devices, particularly in work contexts. They often relied on family for support, which had limitations. They tended to have had less time in formal education. Ageing compounded lack of opportunity, and where people in this group were younger, they were often those who ‘shied away’ from technology. ‘Accomplished learners’ tended to already be engaged, confident, and possess digital skills, usually acquired across their working life.

These learners tended to want to continue learning, and some became volunteers themselves. Thirdly, ‘evolving learners’ tended to have some prior digital experience, often gained later in their working life, and tended to target particular needs and skills. In this Australian study, men were much more likely than women to be in the ‘accomplished learner’ group than the ‘emerging learner’ group, and women were more likely than men to be in the ‘evolving learner’ group versus the ‘accomplished learner’ group. One of the most important take-aways from this research is the need for or value to be found in disaggregating older adults in digital literacy.

An important difference we may see across any group of older adults is their experience of cognitive decline. However, many do not experience a level of cognitive decline such as would materially impact capacity to learn or engage with digital literacy. It is important to balance an awareness of a) the potential spectrum of either typical age-related changes such as slightly slowing processing speed or mild memory decline, and more impactful changes linked to incipient cognitive impairment processes (e.g., related to memory, attention, processing speed, language processing, executive function, visuospatial skills), with b) the risk of stereotyping older adults as cognitively impaired. Given the prevalence of cognitive changes across the lifespan, there is a need to consider the potential relationships

between such change and later life digital literacy.

There is little scientific literature that specifically explores the intersection of cognitive change or decline and digital literacy programmes. However, some studies have recommended bearing in mind when designing programme materials that learners will have different learning paces and some may have a measure of memory (or other cognitive) difficulty (Schirmer et al., 2023).

Research with participants with preserved cognitive functioning and different stages of cognitive decline has demonstrated that worse levels of cognitive decline are associated with both seeing technologies as less relevant to one's life and with greater perceived difficulty in using technology everyday (Rosenberg, Kottorp, Winblad, & Nygård, 2009). There may be sex-related differences in cognitive changes, with women having shown longer preservation of memory recall ability, and men showing longer preservation of visuospatial skills (Ferreira et al., 2013), whereas more recent research has shown that women start from a higher baseline and decline more quickly in general. A very recent, large-scale review and meta-analysis has demonstrated an association between greater use of digital technologies and reduced risk of cognitive impairment or decline (Benge & Scullin, 2025).

2.5.2 The Learning Environment: Flexible, Individual, and Personalised

Secondly, Gates and Wilson-Metzfeld (2022) highlighted the learning environment. Research has reported preferences for in-session practice time, manageable classes sizes, and provision of take-home resources (Gates & Wilson-Metzfeld, 2022). While one study in their review suggested the importance of a structured learning environment with well-defined activities (Castro Rojas et al., 2018), another suggested a preference for flexibility and being able to incorporate different activities (Leedahl et al., 2019). It is the latter which chimes with other research in the area around personalisation and individualisation of programmes (e.g., Finkelstein, We, & Brennan-Ing, 2023).

Schirmer and colleagues' (2023) scoping review of digital competence in older adults found a need for flexible adaptation of programmes to older adults' individual fears, individual experience or lack thereof, and individual physical limitations.

Finkelstein, We, and Brennan-Ing's (2023) research on experiences of using ICT and ICT support services in New York, USA, showed that mere connection with devices and technological support did not lead to greater adoption of digital technology. In fact, people tended not to call upon professional support, and it was pre-existing skills that tended to determine usage. Another interesting

finding in that study was that there is a cohort of learners who do not or cannot generalise certain skills that they have learned from one setting, device, or technology to another. These researchers recommended customised training based on individual needs.

Gates and Wilson-Metzfeld's (2022) review found that personalisation of learning programmes enabled learners to, as they say, find value in digital technologies. Various research favours individualised lessons for learners to develop skills relevant to them (Brown & Strommen, 2018), and to incorporate pre-existing interests for long-term engagement of technology and ability to integrate technology into their everyday lives (Beh, Medell, & Mascitelli, 2018).

Personalised digital literacy training can be combined with existing programmes with complementary aims. Fields and colleagues' (2020) study of one-to-one, in-home digital training incorporated into an existing in-home visiting programme for socially isolated older adults found marginal increases in digital confidence, but considerable increase in use of digital technology.

Whereas Gates and Wilson-Metzfeld's (2022) mentions ways of imparting the value of digital technology upon older adults learners, there is a related point worth making. Older adults may already see such value (and where they do not, this may also result from individual judgement, which ought to be respected). Indeed, Damodaran,

Olphert, and Phipps (2013) put forth based on their findings that "older people value very highly the benefits and independence that computer use gives them, and they are often exceptionally tenacious in trying to remain digitally connected – persisting in the face of many obstacles, and often without awareness or use of existing aids to accessibility" (p. 32). This echoes literature which has clearly found that older adults are more positively than negatively disposed toward technology (Mitzner et al., 2010). Positive attitudes, per Mitzner and colleagues' study for example, include how technology can support activities of interest, can offer convenience, and can offer useful features. Negative attitudes are associated with inconvenience, unhelpful features, and security and reliability concerns.

2.5.3 Attitudinal Barriers

Older adults face attitudinal barriers to use and enjoyment of technology and the development of digital literacy, including ageism. Gates and Wilson-Metzfeld (2022) undertook a systematic review of implementation and delivery of digital skills programmes for older adults, with particular emphasis on geragogy (older adult learning). Their review had findings of relevance. Negative perceptions of ageing influenced programme delivery. Ideas around subjective age and negative attitudes to learners' ages can, according to a qualitative study of eight educators of older adults, lead to learners' self-

exclusion from learning and digital literacy and lower motivation (Tomczyk, Mróz, Potyrała, & Wnęk-Gozdek, 2020). To counteract this, researchers have argued for adaptation to the preferences and physical or cognitive needs (LoBuono et al., 2019).

With respect to ageism, Barrie and colleagues (2021) recommend involving older adults in planning and possibly facilitating the training. Research has also suggested and demonstrated a need for moving beyond mere skill development, and toward addressing both internal, personal barriers and external socio-contextual barriers to digital literacy (Arthanat et al., 2019). Whereas older adults' families, for example, may ascribe to older adult learners a reluctance, lack of affinity, or fear, older adults themselves find a sense of accomplishment, challenge, and competence through literacy training. While Arthanat and colleagues' (2019) study focused on in-home tuition, their findings are transferable to other contexts: surmounting attitudinal and socio-cultural barriers can be achieved through one-to-one tuition. Rather than defining or delineating training based on a catch-all characteristic of age group, effective training programmes will centre individual need and preference.

2.5.4 Involvement

Echoing, Barrie and colleague's (2021) recommendation for involving older adults in planning and facilitating training, there has been insufficient attention to centering the primary stakeholders, i.e., older adults and isolated older adults, in the assessment of digital literacy interventions, and in the assessment of implementation and scale-up planning. Indeed, the specific inclusion of older men in such research is a long-standing gap in the existing literature.

SECTION 3: QUALITATIVE FOCUS GROUPS

This section reports the overall focus group findings. Using thematic analysis, the following four key themes were interpreted from the focus group data:

- Theme 1: (Responding to) The Imperative to Adapt
- Theme 2: Digital Is Emotional and Social
- Theme 3: Practical Skills to Enable Quality-of-Life
- Theme 4: Targeted Programme Delivery

Each of these themes is now outlined and discussed in more detail below.

3.1 Theme 1: (Responding to) The Imperative to Adapt

A number of participants emphasised a sense that adaptation to a digital world is essential, coupled with a fear or reality that they are, or otherwise would be, left behind. Participants discussed at length the increasing inaccessibility of everyday public and private services. This included considerable frustration with the inaccessibility of important aspects of everyday transport (motor tax payments, parking), banking, utilities (electricity billing), leisure (booking of flights), and healthcare (HSE).

There is a desire to remain current with the rapid developments as technology is increasingly incorporated into daily life. The imperative to adapt is not there simply because the world is changing, but even more saliently, ways of doing things are disappearing. Men often mentioned mechanical and computing machines that emerged throughout their working lives—looms, calculators.

“All this writing out stuff and all that – that’s all disappeared, and that’s why I was saying that we should kind of advance a small bit to the people that have the initial course.” (Jimmy)

Digital technology, and digital literacy, are seen as a means to achieve that adaptation. The men are very keen to be learning the next thing in digital technology and digital literacy. This is linked with the theme of **Practical Skills to Enable Quality-of-Life:**

“This is where we need to move on to learn about these things in the next session.” (Jimmy)

“That would be a thing that you could note anyway, just do another Age Action but a bit more advanced, maybe, for the people that have the initial course done.” (Jimmy)

In discussing technological advancement, and with a context of their historical access to and societal expectations around education, there is a strong sense that older men are and feel at a disadvantage relative to digital natives. Formal education has, they say, become so much more important to enable life participation. Digital literacy is couched as one aspect of that education.

“But in our era, in our area, we're all in our 70s... education didn't matter to us that much. Not alone that, but like I think all of us are here, we were all handy with our hands, and I speak for myself. Now, when I was in school, I hated school. Anyway, from day one, all I was interested in was working with my hands, and I was going to do some trade. I wasn't going into an office. The education wasn't as important back in our era, you know, whereas it is ever so important now, the education.” (Odhrán)

Yet that disadvantage is at least somewhat amenable to being overturned through participation in later-life digital literacy education. While terming themselves

‘disadvantaged’, there was a tacit suggestion that they are disadvantaged right now, but that digital literacy and programmes like Age Action’s are levelling that playing field.

“So, has its great advantages as well as I suppose you couldn't call it disadvantages, really, we call it disadvantages because we're not up to speed, whereas the younger kids just flow through it.” (Jimmy)

Alongside this, a high proportion of Men’s Shed attendees, of which DL MEN attendees are a subset, reportedly already have smartphones, and may even have more than one device; “most of the men who have smartphones probably also have another device, right? [...] And I wouldn't say we're unusual in that, either.” (Dónal) The proportion already engaging with digital technology then, whether smartphone or in-car digital media, appears to be high. However, there is also a cohort that does not have a smart device at all, and this includes both Men’s Shed attendees and other older men who represent both older men who reject or are not interested in digital technologies and older men who are living in isolation.

Finally, the idea of an imperative to adapt, and to solve problems, stretches beyond digital technologies and the challenges they present. For some of the men at least, this was simply the way to approach new challenges for which they do not have the skills: learn and adapt.

“Necessity is the mother of all invention. So everything that was ever done in my house, I had to do it because when I had [family] I couldn’t afford to pay anyone to do it, so I always reckon as long as you can read, you can learn. So get, get your act together, read and find out how to do it. And when I was working [...], I would tune in the machines. And there was this, this guy beside me, he was great at plumbing, and there was this other guy beside me, he was great at electrics. And anything I wanted to know, I’d ask those and anything they’d want to know about putting in bathrooms or tiling like they’d ask me, and we’d help each other out.” (Bobby)

3.2 Theme 2: Digital Is Emotional and Social

The second theme centres on the emotional responses and reactions to digital literacy as a concept and the programme itself. Fear and confidence are central emotional responses (which would be consistent with wider literature around older adults' interaction with technology), and the amelioration of loneliness was also an important topic. However, there are suggestions of a more nuanced and holistic emotional landscape around digital literacy. Additionally, and as we will also see below in a subsequent theme with respect to practical literacy to enable quality-of-life, older men also responded to digital with excitement and joy as they explored the pursuit of hobbies. Men identified a specific, and in their view gendered, emotional response to figuring out how to use a technology or how it works – 'kick' or 'buzz'.

3.2.1 Fear as a barrier

Participants strongly emphasised what they termed 'fear' ("fear", "afraid", "frightened") as a barrier to both participating in the digital transition and participation in digital literacy courses which would aid the adaptation to digital technologies. They outlined their own fear and general fear amongst the cohort of older men, but they also illustrated this sense of fear with stories and case examples, which were sometimes quite detailed, about

specific men they knew who rejected technology out of hand. A person may have and even be shown how to use a phone, but may abandon the technology altogether and not carry a mobile phone with them when out and about.

This, they say, is driven by fear, and specifically a fear of making mistakes, of causing problems. Largely this was linked to social faux pas or being a nuisance to other technology users, but it was also linked with security and privacy concerns, and exposure to security risks particularly given the proliferation of digital fraud and scams.

"What I found with people here is that they were afraid of doing it. They were afraid that it's passing by and they wouldn't be able to keep up with things on the phone and on the laptops, you know? And I think that's the biggest with the Age Action here, it's the fear for people, the fear that they won't be able to do it, you know. And I think that should be kind of instilled in people. They can take baby steps, and they will learn something from it." (Jimmy)

“I used to be nervous, and still am, of cutting people off, right, or answering back to one of these [scam] calls, you know? Yeah, it did actually make me afraid. Someone said to me, you won't do any damage. And apparently I knocked a load of people off WhatsApp!”
(Declan)

This fear of technology may be a long-standing fear; not necessarily one which has developed in response to contemporary digital technologies. Additionally, there are men who it seems are historically quite happy working with analogue or mechanical technologies, but for whom digital was a step too far.

“I kept avoiding computers because I was afraid of them. So, it would have made work that much easier for me, but I did.”
(Odhrán)

Folded into this is a similar wariness about artificial intelligence (AI), or at least how AI is used. While there was acknowledgement of the advanced capabilities of high technology, concern was expressed about the potential negative impacts of AI, from displacement of social roles (e.g., ‘making a living’) to unethical use and rights violations.

Exchange:

Bobby: “AI now, is a bit frightening. [...] It's a bit scary.”

Alf: “*Very much so.*”

Bobby: “You know, implications are very scary. Technology can go too far, too you know [...] if technology takes over you, you can go too far, you know, I think you can go too far.”

So, while the men are engaged in a digital literacy programme, and thus could be seen as unaware of technological developments, they discuss in considerable depth the implications of the development of artificial intelligence, the use of artificial intelligence in geopolitical conflict, technology entrepreneurship, and online fraud. Many of the men are well versed, and keenly interested in, the uses and implications of advanced technology, which is often interwoven with skepticism or fear; it is merely the practical skills in certain areas that they want guidance with.

Concern and apprehension also comes through quite strongly with respect to digital security, and fraud and the proliferation of new ways to defraud.

“The one thing, the only thing I'd be afraid about is, is someone accessing your bank account. That's one of the biggest worries I think about, about the whole thing. You know what I mean and like and all the all the calls I get, ‘Oh, your computer, is, is...’” (Bobby)

Exchange:

Alf: "But the girl on the phone was telling me, 'Now, keep your phone open'. I don't know whether she knew I'd to drive 10 miles to [place]. So I happened to ring one of my daughters. [They] laughed. [...] "So it looks... sounds so genuine." So [they] says, "Don't answer the phone in the morning."

Bobby: *"It does. It does sound genuine."*

3.2.2 Loneliness and Isolation

Participants spoke to loneliness, which is somewhat separable from both aloneness and from isolation. Digital technologies bridge the gap for people, and provide considerable benefits. This is linked with how DL-MEN fits with the Men's Shed setting, where Men's Sheds are "a reasonably significant part of everybody's life." (Dónal). The Men's Shed social setting is likely an important factor for attendance and engagement with the programmes.

"Even with phone calls, texts and even WhatsApp him to talk [colloquialism] or whatever. But, you know, that's a huge benefit for him, you know, for him, anyway, it's a huge benefit." (Odhrán)

Men in the DL MEN programme may or may not have partners or families and the same is true for those who do not participate in DL MEN. There is a clear separation between loneliness for which older men might seek and be in a position to seek remedy for at a Men's Shed or through DL MEN, and a social isolation from almost all

contact, friends, or a social setting like the Men's Shed. This is a reality for many. Participants relayed stories of isolated older men, where again it is fear, or perhaps a more nuanced feeling of reluctance or trepidation, of not being able to use or adapt to technology that might be the operative emotion or response that might function as both a barrier to using technology and to social participation.

"A lot of people doesn't have that, you know? I mean, there are men out there living on their own in the countryside. They never got married and and it's amazing, it's amazing how you can be in contact with the rest of the world with the computer or the phone, and there are men, people out there sitting and they have nothing, you know what I mean? And they've never, they've never got into it, you know, I mean, and supposed, a bit reluctant to grasp it, have a go at technology. You know, they might be afraid it's too that they wouldn't be able to, you know, get the hang of it, you know." (Bobby)

“I'd go home and I'd forget what was after being done, right? You know? Like you could go there and think, to yourself, 'What is this now?' And ask a family member. Where I had none of that, you know, and that's what I found hard about it.” (Declan)

3.2.3 Confidence

In almost parallel to ideas of fear, and fear functioning as a barrier to both technology use and digital literacy programme engagement, we see considerable emphasis on confidence. In conferring confidence, the digital literacy programme helps to both overcome limitations with digital literacy and technology-related fear.

“I would consider myself prior - prior to this - being totally computer illiterate, but I've picked up a lot, and I am a bit more confident operating the computer on my phone.”
(Odhrán)

3.2.4 Buzz

The men discussed differences between how men and women approach technology. While acknowledging that it should not be generalised to all men and women, they discussed how in their view men are more curious about technology in

general, are more interested in figuring out how technology works, and get more of a 'buzz' or a 'kick' out of figuring out how to use a technology or problem solving with respect to technology. This may link to masculine identities. One distinction they draw is thus that women are more interested in the functionality and end result of using the technology. Below are excerpts from an exchange on the topic.

“I mean, like, I'd be more tech savvy now than my wife. She's a, she was a [profession], you know, so she depends on, but she just, she just doesn't have the curiosity.” (Dónal)

“Yeah, figuring things, I think men are more curious. Most men, I'd say, are more curious in that perspective [...] I think they're more interested in, yeah, like you won't see, you won't see many women out with drones around like that. You see men with them, you know. I mean, yeah. And that kind of technology, that kind of stuff. [...] I think, I think men like those kind of challenges. Yeah, I think I don't... It's not fair to say, I wouldn't say all women are like that, but there's a lot of women that would be comparable, you know, I mean, but I think mostly, you know, I think it's a male thing.”
(Bobby)

“I'd say men probably do actually now. Just say yeah, probably get more of a kick out.” (Dónal)

“I think so yeah, like, there's women who just want the functionality.”
(Bobby)

“But insofar as we have to figure out how to do it, like, for example, [...] I Googled whether or not WhatsApp had a translate function in it, which it does, and figured out how to use it so that I could type for her the message in English into a box, but it appeared in the WhatsApp dialogue in Spanish, you know, [...]. I asked [man] to do the same thing in reverse. He wasn't clued in enough to do it. But I got a kick out of figuring it out, yeah, how to do that, versus my wife's point of view. She just wanted the directions [...], you know, and to be able to do the thing. And if she'd figured it out, I don't think she would have got the same buzz that I got out of the figuring out, okay, she would have got the benefit of being able to do it.” (Dónal)

There is a suggestion that they see that this distinction may become less stark with generational change.

“I think the younger girls now are more into it than, would say, than they used to be. [...] They're all into, well-up on technology, you know.”
(Bobby)

3.3 Theme 3: Practicality to Enable Quality-of-Life

The third theme centres upon the desire for practical education, practical literacy to enable quality-of-life and the social communication, activities, and community participation that are important to achieving it. What older men like about digital literacy programmes like Age Action's DL MEN is its practical focus. Older men want to pay motor tax, buy parking tickets, book flights, pursue hobbies online, and use

everyday social communication tools such as WhatsApp). The key element is that what they want to pursue is linked to their own preferences and tends to be practical, and linked to problem solving or meeting particular challenges to enhancing their quality-of-life.

“WhatsApp has become the dominant way of communicating online. What's great about it is, apart from being free, is that it's pictorial as well as word based, yes and video based, so people share jokes they might not always be all that funny or whatever, but yeah, so, and it's, it's just so fast, and you can have groups as you know, as well as individual content, by flexible kind of form of communication” (Dónal)

“My boys set up a WhatsApp kind of thing and put me on, you know, then I learned to have another one behind that didn't put me on. [laughter] They didn't put me on in case they want to talk about me.” (Bobby)

“I have friends in Australia and New Zealand. And you get surprised someday, you get a message from them.” (Alf)

“I got a computer laptop, and I received emails and you send them back. I wouldn't go into the banking or I wouldn't go into anything like that. So, I used to see people years ago with the phone and I said 'Jeez, I'm never goin' to get one of them. Here I am now. [...] I'd like to learn a bit more on the laptop.” (Johnny)

They are excited by the possibilities of new media, like YouTube, which facilitates engagement with interests, hobbies, and pastimes. They also use and enjoy, in perhaps complicated ways, digital games. One participant described using a mobile game as a sleep aid.

“The only thing I find about the phone, the games are very addictive, right? Yeah, very addictive. And if you play games, I do now alright, and I find it very addictive. What I do find: they're a great help to put me to sleep, but it would have been, I start playing the game, and I'm gone.” (Odhrán)

This can be contrasted with more strictly rigid curricular programmes, including those which might have a focus on literacy around productivity tools. Yet, PowerPoint and Excel are not interesting to older men (except where perhaps an individual might express that particular preference).

“We have, we've had two kinds of computer courses, I can call them that, or digital skills courses here recently, one was from the [PLACE]. It was in a classroom setting here, where everybody sits down with their PC, with a prescribed curriculum. And some people got a lot out of it, but other people said they were being taught things they didn't need to learn, like, say, Excel, or PowerPoint. Yeah. On the other hand, the digital skills, the one to one, people said, well, they were able to pitch it exactly at what I wanted.” (Dónal)

“And when I was promoting the program to the guys in the shed, I kept emphasising all the time, that it's up to you to say what you want learn.” (Dónal)

“And a lot of the time would be wasted on the on me, you know, if that was the case, because there was a lot that stuff I wouldn't need, you know, I don't, don't really need, as I said to you, there practicality, things that I would use from day to day, you know, even, even if it goes to looking up the RIP, you know what I mean, or, you know, things that I would use in everyday use, you know, that's, that's all I want to know about it.” (Bobby)

“Absolutely. Yeah, it's like [NAME] said, what he wanted to learn was how to buy things in an... how to do an auction online. Yeah, that's what he was interested in finding out how to do, not PowerPoint or Excel.”
(Dónal)

3.4 Theme 4: Targeted Programme Delivery

The final of four themes is Targeted Programme Delivery, representing the shaping and tailoring of programme mode, delivery, and logistics to match the needs of older men in Ireland. Under this theme, there are sub-themes of a) a preference for one-to-one tuition, b) considerations for time and place of learning.

3.4.1 Preference for One-to-One Tuition

Participants were complimentary about the programme tutors and the personalised attention they received, finding the tutors helpful, patient, and supportive.

“The man from Age Action showed me what to do. And like that was a clear point for me.” (Trevor)

“The fellas here were brilliant. [...] not just the fella that I had [...] he was very good, he had patience.” (Brendan)

Participants emphasized the benefits of one-on-one tutoring over group sessions for effective learning. One-to-one tutoring makes the programme more accessible and facilitates participants to engage with the tutor. Where logistical difficulties arise, participants would be happy with two-to-one also.

One-to-one tutoring is also not open to the same issues as might arise in group structures because of the group structures, where participants might engage in joking around and thus not learning from the programme.

“Well, the one thing that I find is that is a one to one, because we had [...] maybe four or five years ago, we done a computer course up in [place], which is a community-based and there were eight of us. And we were messing. You know, it was messy because there was fellas asking questions, silly questions for the want of a better word, now. And then you had fellas making funny remarks, then about it. And we learned nothing, really. But on a one to one, it's the only way to learn it. In a group session, I think it's a waste for for our age group. In a group session, I think is a waste of time. One to one is the best.”
(Odhrán)

3.4.1 Time and Place

The men spoke to logistical and mode-of-delivery considerations related to continued implementation. The Men's Shed is an ideal setting for delivering digital literacy programmes, because,

"It's a reasonably significant part of everybody's life. Very few men that just flit in and flit out." (Dónal)

This also belies the social and emotional aspects of digital literacy and, more so, attending a digital literacy programme; it's part of the social engagement inherent in attending the Men's Shed and participating in its activities. Many older men may also not have family or friends on whom to rely, or who are always available, for support using technology.

The time of year in which the programme takes place was one thing that was deemed worthy of consideration, with winter time being seen as ideal, as older men might not be 'out and about':

"Even if it was in the winter, like it'd be more suitable in the winter, because people, you know, they won't be out and about like and they won't be on holiday." (Jimmy)

In addition to favouring the one-to-one delivery noted elsewhere, there was favourability toward making available recordings online so that the course can be pursued in a self-paced manner. This would allow learners to follow up in-person classes and check and reinforce their learning. This may also help men who do not have a lot of social connections or family to rely on for support with digital literacy.

"I suppose, recordings online, if you could get sort of like a programme that explains it and you can take your own time, and you can go through it, and you have a chance that, if it doesn't work, you can go back and check it again, [...] something like that, like, would be very helpful to people." (Gerry)

SECTION 4: PARTICIPATORY DESIGN WORKSHOP

To leverage the key insights generated from the focus groups reported in the previous section, a final multi-stakeholder participatory design session was conducted. The overarching goals of this session was:

- To briefly summarise and share tentative insights generated from both the evidence review and the focus group discussions
- To critically reflect on the interpreted personas derived from the evidence and the focus groups
- To ensure all voices could participate in ideating what the future of DL programmes within AAI should look like into the future, with reference to what is or is not working.

4.1 Personas

Four broad personas were interpreted from our literature review and focus groups to scaffold our interactions with the participatory design session. The use of personas was chosen for several key ethical and best practice guidelines. In the first instance, as personas are fictitious characters (but are nonetheless relatable), it allows participants to speak to the personas rather than invoking (potentially sensitive) personal experiences which can be a known barrier for older men's engagement. Additionally,

personas allow representation for individuals who may not be present in the research (such as Persona 1, Tony). Finally, it allows all participants to critically discuss all personas as opposed to just personal experience. Together, both participants' personal experiences coupled with their critical reflection on personas can allow for a richer and purposeful interaction.

Figure 1 is the personas summary presented to participants during the participatory design session. Four personas were constructed to capture the types of participants within the DL programme:

4.1.1 Persona 1 - Tony

Throughout the planning of this report, it was acknowledged that it was crucial to include the perspective of older men who, for reasons which may not be fully clear, never engage with DL programmes (nor other comparable programmes). Despite evidence that suggests the likely benefits of DL programmes, there appears to be a consistent pattern whereby non-engagement is a norm for a certain cohort of older men. More broadly, when considering 'what works' in DL programmes, best practice research evaluations are wary of survivorship bias when looking at programmes of willing

participants. That is, if we only look at the older men who choose to join the programme, what would our evaluations look like if we evaluated the experiences of all men? If DL programmes only ‘work’ or are of appeal to certain subgroups of older men, how can we address this issue?

4.1.2 Persona 2 - Larry

To reflect the known drop-out rates across some DL programmes both in Ireland and in the wider literature, this persona was created to capture the issue of attrition and engagement. Whilst it is not immediately evident as to why dropout trends remain a key challenge, there are some reasons offered within the literature. Some of the factors associated with observed dropout rates may include: post-COVID effects, ineffective engagement, a lack of individualised programmes, logistical or practical reasons (such as commuting challenges or health concerns), or a mismatch between participant expectations and programme realities. As these dropout risks were acknowledged by our Research Advisory group, and are a consistent trend within the research literature, this persona was built to explore why this pattern exists.

4.1.3 Persona 3 - Tim

In contrast to the previous persona, this persona was created to mirror the many positively engaged participants in DL programmes. The core purpose of this persona was to

help understand the factors underpinning what is working with DL programmes, from content to engagement strategies and other potentially unknown factors. Understanding what is currently working is pivotal to consolidating these ingredients into the future

4.1.4 Persona 4 - Charlie

Finally, our fourth persona was ideated on the basis of the interesting and differing motivations of older men who engage with DL programmes. The perceived benefits and outcomes can sometimes be at odds with the learning objectives. For example, within the literature, it has been observed that some cohorts of older men engage with DL programmes solely for the social and community benefits, and not the DL content. This presents an interesting dilemma with regards to desirable outcomes - where an older man does not improve any DL outcomes but has a very positive social experience, how should we interpret this?

Figure 1. Personas Summary

4.2 Our Three Guiding Questions

To ensure a scaffolded and efficient participatory design session could be facilitated within a very short duration (of approximately one hour), three key questions were posed:

1. Based on what you have just heard, what is your first impression?
2. If Age Action had unlimited resources, what should they do with the DL Programme?
3. How should Age Action (re)design the Digital Literacy Programme? with prompts regarding: rollout, scale-up, location(s), content/structure, reach and impact).

Following a brief presentation of the above personas, participants were invited to offer initial reactions to this content (Q1) and initiate conversations related to this. This was designed to organically initiate interactions without direct reference to any one specific programme. From here, a hypothetical question challenged participants to think about what an ideal DL programme could look like regardless of resources limitations (Q2). This was purposely designed to free participants from their prior experiences and expectations to allow them to more informally ideate on “ideal world” DL programmes. Lastly, and more specifically, participants were asked to think about the potential (re)design of the DL programme with respect to practical aspects.

4.3 Key Results from the Participatory Session

4.3.1 The need for personalised and agile iterations

In light of the four personas, participants all shared DL programme experiences that demonstrated the need for considering how future rollouts could afford greater personalisation and programme agility to what are different types of participation. That is, given the unique needs of men who may have differing baseline competences and motivations in addition to progression rates, how can future DL programmes adapt and personalise in real-time?

4.3.2 Embracing social and emotional factors

A consistent theme within the data related to the many social and emotional factors that were implicated in the experiences of men in DL programmes. Participants spoke to the key relational components of the programme including: community-building, sense of rapport, and a sense of personal growth related to learning progress. Within these points, the emotions related to one's self-confidence were discussed in-depth. The need to understand where one's baseline level of self-confidence is at the inception of a DL programme was seen as important in informing how to potentially tailor the programme or communication style for the given individual.

Interestingly, the role of self-confidence was seen as both a potential barrier to, and facilitator of, DL programme engagement. Despite the learning outcomes attached to DL programme components, participants emphasised the need to better target self-confidence early on the programme, and encourage consolidation of this feeling throughout. Where participants may gain new skills (such as flight bookings, smartphone usage), these may become redundant if participants lose a sense of confidence in applying them.

4.3.3 Respecting participant autonomy, non-responsiveness and varied experiences

Primarily prompted by the Tony persona, all participants acknowledged the challenging reality that there will likely always be a (would-be) participant who will not experience DL programmes positively. One participant shared an experience of poor learning outcomes for his group following participation ("I don't think we were any wiser at the end"), and everyone recognised the men who dropped off the programme, or the men who did not show up in the first instance. Central to these discussions was the need to respect the autonomy of such experiences without inadvertently invoking stigma, pressure to participate, or further alienation. Instead, continuing our energy to understand the likely many complex factors underpinning these challenges was underlined.

SECTION 5: RECOMMENDATIONS

The overall data suggests that of the men that do participate in DL programmes, there a wide range of positive experiences reported, enhanced skills and indirect benefits also. As Age Action continues to develop and refine digital literacy initiatives for older men, our research highlights a number of critical considerations for the design, implementation, and scale-up of such programmes. We set out a series of recommendations drawing from our review of extant literature and programmes in Ireland and abroad, insights gleaned from our focus group research with older men (DL MEN participants), and insights from our participatory design workshop consultation with multiple stakeholders involved in digital literacy programmes.

Broadly, our recommendations point to the need for a person-centred, context-sensitive approach that recognises the diverse experiences, preferences, and emotional responses older men bring to digital engagement and digital literacy.

The recommendations emphasise practical, everyday literacies delivered through one-to-one tutoring, as DL MEN already does. This is coupled with particular emphasis on social connection, confidence-building, and the emotional landscape of learning. They reflect our broader

understanding that successful digital literacy programmes are not solely about transferring skills, but about creating meaningful learning environments that respect individuals' starting points, preferences, and the wider circumstances shaping their digital participation and their lives. In particular, we call attention to the unique motivations, challenges, and opportunities involved in engaging older men—some of whom may be highly motivated to adapt to digital life, while others remain hesitant or disengaged altogether.

The following recommendations aim to guide future implementation, scale-up, and innovation in digital literacy programming for older men. They span four broad themes: programme focus, considering who participates, programme delivery logistics (within which we consider facilitation of social engagement), and centring emotions and gendered responses, each reinforcing the importance of personalisation and empathy in delivering impactful digital literacy education.

5.1 Programme focus

1. Prioritise one-to-one tutoring

One-to-one tutoring enhances programme accessibility, making it easier for participants to engage with the tutor, to learn, and to shape and personalise their digital literacy education. While the social aspect of attending digital literacy education is integral, important, and highly valued, the tuition itself should emphasise one-to-one contact. One-to-one tutoring also helps to circumvent a tendency among some groups to ‘mess around’ or joke too much, as research participants have said, during the learning activities, which can detract from programme effectiveness.

2. Digital literacy programmes should provide practical, personalized digital skills training and overall literacies focused on participants' everyday needs and quality-of-life

Older men seem to have a strong preference for literacies that specifically help them navigate everyday life, and enhance everyday quality-of-life: using smartphones, using communication apps (e.g., WhatsApp), booking parking tickets, paying motor tax, booking air travel. Older men are less interested, in general, in any programme that would centre a curriculum of productivity tools (e.g., Excel, PowerPoint). This

personalisation will need to account for divergent baselines and links directly to recommendation 3 below.

3. Sustainable implementation, scale-up, and spread of the programme should explore offering regular technology refresher courses, or more advanced material, to help participants stay up-to-date

Older men have reported wanting to build upon the skills and literacy that they have acquired. They want to keep tackling new challenges, whether that be new aspects of or barriers to community participation or more complex challenges (such as booking flights with two-factor authentication), new challenges in online security and fraud prevention, or learning about and meeting the challenges related to the proliferation of generative AI. This links to the previous recommendation around personalised, practical skills and literacies that link to quality-of-life.

4. Consider the appeal of older men's willingness to respond to the imperative to adapt to digital landscapes

Older men participating in this research study exhibited an enterprising spirit and are willing and very keen to respond to what they see as an absolute imperative to adapt to a rapidly changing world and its digital landscapes. Given careful

consideration, such a sense of imperative coupled with the willingness to meet that imperative could be leveraged to promote digital literacy and to ensure that programmes respond to and meet older men's adaptive needs.

This is linked to the recommendation to provide practical, personalized digital skills training focused on participants' everyday needs and quality-of-life (recommendation 2) and likely to considering the roles of fear, confidence, and positive emotions (recommendations 9 - 11), and considering the gendered role of deriving 'buzz' from figuring out technologies (recommendation 12).

5.2 Considering Who Participates

5. Close consideration should be given to the question of 'Who participates, and who does not?'

Hard-to-reach older men are likely to be a diverse group. Some may want to participate, or may have participated or attempted to participate in the DL MEN programme, but they may experience barriers to programme engagement. Secondly and alternatively, they may, for various reasons, have difficulty enjoying the programme, whether because of personal preference, local conditions, logistical issues, limited accessibility, or other reasons. Ongoing, targeted engagement will help to tease apart individuals'

reasons for non-engagement or disengagement. Thirdly, some older men may simply not wish to participate at all in digital literacy or even digital life. Such choices can be respected while continuing to consider alternative quality-of-life enhancing offerings for older men. Such offerings might include those that may help them connect with others socially as they prefer, engage in activities important to them, or participate in their community life.

5.3 Logistics

6. Consider the role of location and facilities to foster social and peer engagement

Similar to the older men who attended Men's Sheds and had a positive connection with the Men's Shed as a site of delivery, there is a clear connection between location and facilities with the social aspect to, and motivation for, sustained attendance. Stakeholders have indicated that, under certain circumstances where the social element of the programme is not facilitated, they may be less suitable for roll-out of a digital literacy programme. Certain libraries, for example, do not have the facilities to offer opportunities for informal social engagement, an informal chat with a cup of tea, or similar. Centring the social element of the digital literacy programme is likely to enhance continued implementation and spread of the DL MEN programme.

7. Future scale-up should continue to consider scheduling of programme delivery

Research participants, for example, recommended that DL MEN be delivered in winter time when people have good availability to attend.

8. Consider parallel provision of online support videos

Participants seemed pleased with the present structure and delivery of DL MEN. However, one suggestion was the provision of parallel content online so that participants can return to refresh on particular skills or literacies at their own pace.

5.4 Centring Emotions and Gendered Responses

9. Continued implementation and scale-up should consider the role of fear as a barrier to digital engagement and programme participation

Fear has long been acknowledged as a barrier to engagement with and use of technology. In the case of digital literacy programmes, fear might be ameliorated by emphasis on opportunities for social engagement, emphasis on one-to-one tuition (reducing risk of embarrassment or ‘being a nuisance’), personalisation and the pursuit of specific literacies, and linking digital literacy to

everyday, practical tasks and problem solving that will enhance attendees quality-of-life. Fear or apprehension is multifaceted, and may relate not only to digital unknowns, the potential uses and misuses of highly advanced technology like artificial intelligence, and risk of fraud-related victimisation, but also to ‘causing nuisance’ to others or committing social faux pas. Each of these fears or apprehensions may be addressed in turn with the digital literacy programme. It may be the case that fears may be addressed indirectly through focus on one-to-one tuition (recommendation 1), practical literacies for everyday life and quality-of-life (recommendation 2), continual and/or refresher offerings (recommendation 3), leveraging the enterprising spirit and men’s willingness to respond to the imperative to adapt to digital landscapes (recommendation 4), and the role of delivery location and facilities in fostering opportunities for peer engagement (recommendation 6).

10. Implementation and scale-up should continually consider and foster confidence as both programme outcome and facilitator of programme participation

Confidence has also long been acknowledged in the scientific literature as an important aspect of adaptation to and use of technology. Participants in the present research

emphasised the confidence-building nature of the DL MEN programme; confidence was an important outcome for them and an operative factor in attending and learning how to adapt to new digital landscapes and meet practical challenges. Focusing on building confidence early in the programme and continuing to build upon and maintain that throughout is likely to continue to prove fruitful. Such confidence will likely also help older men to continue to independently pursue their own further digital literacy development.

11. Continued implementation should consider the role of positive responses to technology and ‘getting technology to work’

Excitement and joy can be observed with respect to using new technologies in one’s daily life, even for unintended uses (for example, using games as a sleep aid), the enablement of practical tasks, facilitation of the pursuit of interests, and opening up new possibilities. Even simply figuring out how to use a particular technology can generate a positive response, or ‘buzz’.

12. Implementation and scale-up should consider the possibly gendered ‘buzz’ or ‘kick’ that men derive from figuring out technology or getting technology to work

Men reported seeing a difference between how men and women—at least of their generation—approach technology. They feel men are more curious or interested in figuring out, or working out the mechanics of a particular technology, whereas women are more interested in the end-result or functionality, and more likely to use new devices recreationally. Relatedly, they get more of a ‘kick’ or ‘buzz’ out of the figuring out. This sense of curiosity or buzz could be considered or incorporated into continued implementation to appeal to men. Indeed, there may be men, as there were in the present study’s focus groups, who might have a history of fear or avoidance of expressly digital technology, but who might be comfortable with more analogue or mechanical technology. Here, the focus on getting a kick out of problem-solving and figuring out digital technologies might generate appeal. This may also link to men’s interest in ‘moving on a bit’ and tackling new challenges, whether they be practical tasks to enable quality-of-life (e.g., booking parking or flights, or quite advanced explorations of developments in artificial intelligence).

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APPENDICES

Literature Review Search Strategy

Table 3: Systematic search strategy

Field	PEO	Domain	Syntax
1	Population	Older adults	(Old* OR elder* OR geriatric* OR geront* OR aging OR ageing OR senior* OR "Late Life" OR "Later Life" OR Retire* OR matur*)
2	Exposure	Digital Literacy Programmes	((Digital literacy OR digital skills OR digital capability OR digital ability OR computer skills OR computer literacy OR computer ability OR computer capability OR IT skills OR technolog* skills OR technolog* literacy OR ICT literacy OR ICT skills) AND (program* OR course OR intervention OR training))
3	Outcome	Implementation	(implement* OR format OR structure OR Accept* OR enrol* abandon* OR dropout OR adopt* OR adhere* OR scale OR spread OR cover* OR develop* OR expan* OR sustain*)
4	Final search strategy: Field 1 AND Field 2 AND Field 3		